

A conservation management tool for functional objects

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with

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Conservation Management Tool for Functional Objects

PRELIMINARIES	PLANNING	IMPLEMENTATION
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STEP ONE	WHAT IS IT?
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STEP TWO	SIGNIFICANCE ASSESSMENT
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STEP THREE	CONSERVATION OBJECTIVES
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STEP FOUR	TREATMENT PLAN
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Level of Operation

Appearance Objective

Use/application in the museum

Step 1: Assessment of museum readiness

- Aims of the museum
- Existing policies
- Impacts on museum environment
- Resources for ongoing maintenance
- Location for work
- Location for operation

Step 2: Curatorial, physical and resource assessment

- Curatorial assessment
- Physical assessment
- Resources assessment

Curatorial Assessment

- Object description
- History and provenance of the object
- Research similar objects

Physical assessment

- Object description
- Condition of the fabric
- Identification of alterations
- Conditions of functions

Resource assessment

- Resources available to commence and continue
- Exhibition/storage restrictions
- Space required for treatment
- Movement requirements
- Museum use
- Space required for operation

Step 3: Significance assessment

Significance is:

The aesthetic, historic, scientific, social or spiritual value that an object, collection or place has for past, present and future generations.

It refers not just to the physical fabric or appearance of an object. Rather, it incorporates all of the elements that contribute to an object's meaning, including its context, history and uses.

(Significance, 2001, Collections Council of Australia)

Step 4: Conservation Objectives

- Function
- Form
- Use

Levels of operation

1. No operation
2. Minimal operation and tight controls
3. Low levels of operation and considerable controls
4. Medium levels of operation and medium control
5. High levels of operation and limited controls

Determining operation

Risk management matrix

Risk Rating Matrix

Impact	Likelihood				
	Rare	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
Catastrophic	moderate	moderate	high	critical	critical
Major	low	moderate	moderate	high	critical
Moderate	low	moderate	moderate	moderate	high
Minor	very low	low	moderate	moderate	moderate
Insignificant	very low	very low	low	low	moderate

Application of risk management matrix

Function		Analysis of risk		
Identify the function	What are the risks to personnel and the object	Consequence	Likelihood	Risk level
Fly the plane	Object: crash = loss of object Personnel: crash = death or serious injury	Catastrophic	Moderate	HIGH
Operate the propeller	Object: mechanical failure = loss of parts (not original to object)	Moderate	Moderate	SIGNIFICANT
	Personnel: injury from starting the propeller	Moderate	Unlikely	MEDIUM
	Personnel: walking into the propeller	Moderate	Unlikely	MEDIUM

Using the results to determine operation

Risk rating	Minimum operation threshold	Maximum operation threshold
HIGH	Level 1 – no operation	Level 2 – Minimal operation
SIGNIFICANT	Level 2 – Minimal operation	Level 3 – Low levels of operation
MEDIUM	Level 3 – Low levels of operation	Level 4 – Medium levels of operation
LOW	Level 4 – Medium levels of operation	Level 5 – High levels of operation

Determining operation: Barclay's model

- Rarity
- Fragility
- State

Five star system in each

Rarity

Unique *****

Rare ****

Historic ***

Common **

Replaceable *

Fragility

Highest *****

High ****

Medium ***

Low **

Safest *

State

Perfect *****

Original ****

Used ***

Altered **

Transformed *

Application of Barclay's model to determine levels of operation

15 stars	Level 1 – No operation
12-14 stars	Level 2 – Minimal operation
9-11 stars	Level 3 – Low levels of operation
5-8 stars	Level 4 – medium levels of operation
3-4 stars	Level 5 – high levels of operation

Conservation objectives

- Appearance
- Proposed use/interpretation

Step 5: Treatment Plan

Treatment of the function – establishing the level of operation to be achieved.

- Identification of modifications required for legal operation
- Assessment of the viability and worthiness of operation

Resource assessment

- Budget
- Skills
- Materials and equipment
- Space

Step 6: Treatment implementation

- Treatment of functional components and external surfaces
- Development of display, storage and interpretation systems

Step 7: Lifecycle preservation plan

- Operational guidelines
- Handling guidelines
- Inspection and maintenance plan

Operational guidelines

- Level of operation
- Risk assessment for operation
- Safe operating procedure
- Authorised operators and operator competencies
- Schedule for operation
- Operating log

Handling guidelines

- Risk assessment for handling
- Safe handling procedure

Inspection and maintenance plan

- Inspection plan and schedule
- Maintenance plan and schedule
- Templates for record keeping

Applying the tool at the National Motor Museum of Australia

Case studies – the Favourite Motorcycle

The Favourite Motorcycle

The Talbot Overlander

The top of one of the Depot Sandhills (first trip).

The Talbot Overlander

The Talbot Overlander

Transcontinental BMW

Transcontinental BMW

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